

Molecular Adducts of Triphenyltin Isothiocyanate with Some N⁻, O⁻, and S⁻ Donor Ligands

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Twelve new molecular adducts of triphenyltin isothiocyanate with several N⁻, O⁻, and S⁻ donor ligands have been synthesized and characterized through elemental analysis, molecular weight, molar conductance, IR and PMR data.

HOLLOWAY *et al*¹ reported the acceptor properties of triphenyltin isothiocyanate with some N⁻, and O⁻, donor ligands. The present study was undertaken to examine in detail the interaction of triphenyltin isothiocyanate with some N⁻, O⁻, and S⁻ donors such as tetramethyl ethylenediamine (TMEN), propylenediamine (pn), ethyleneurea (EU), 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone (1-Me-2-pyr), dimethylformamide (DMF), 2-picoline N-oxide (2-picO), hexamethylphosphoramide (HMPA), dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO), dibutylsulphoxide (Bu₂SO), tetramethylthiuramdisulphide (TMTS), 2-aminothiazole (Atz), and triphenylphosphine sulphide (Ph₃PS). The structure of the newly synthesized adducts has been suggested on the basis of elemental analysis, molecular weight, molar conductance, IR and PMR data.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by the direct interaction of Lewis acid with the bases in a dry box flushed with nitrogen using benzene-acetone mixture as a solvent.

In a representative experiment, to a solution of Lewis acid (5 m moles) in about 15 ml of the solvent, was added a solution of the excess ligand (10 m moles) in about 20 ml of the same solvent and the mixture was refluxed for 2-3 h. Excess of the solvent was distilled off and the residual solution was kept overnight in a deep freeze to yield a crystalline adduct. In cases where the solution failed to crystallise, the adduct was precipitated by addition of excess diethyl ether, hexane and/or pet-ether. The crude product was recrystallised from the same solvent, washed and dried.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) indicate 1:1 (metal: ligand) stoichiometry except in adducts with propylenediamine and 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone, where the molar ratios are 1:4 and 1:2 respectively.

The adducts are sharp melting crystalline solids excepting that of Bu₂SO, which is a viscous mass. All compounds are soluble in common organic solvents but insoluble in carbon tetrachloride. They are thermally stable and unaffected by atmospheric oxygen and moisture. The molar conductance (10⁻⁴M solutions in nitrobenzene at 30-35°: 5.81-12.18 mhos cm²/mole) and the molecular weight data are in agreement with the proposed stoichiometry. They support monomeric character and non-electrolytic nature of the adducts.

IR Spectra: The IR spectra of the adducts were recorded and frequencies of diagnostic value are discussed below:

The appearance of a strong band at ~2050 cm⁻¹ assigned to CN stretching and at 845±15 cm⁻¹ due to CS stretching mode in the spectra of all the molecular adducts, definitely suggest the presence of N-bonded thiocyanate².

N-donor adducts: The coordination through nitrogen atom in the complexes of TMEN and pn is evident from—

(a) the positive shift of νCN by 20 cm⁻¹ due to donation of electrons from the nitrogen atom to Sn atom and (b) the negative shift of νNH₂ (3050 cm⁻¹) in the adduct of pn as compared to (3320 cm⁻¹) in the free ligand.

O-donor adducts containing X=O; (X≡C, N, P or S).

In the spectra of the adducts of EU, DMF and 1-Me-2-pyr; νCO appears at 1600 cm⁻¹ as compared to its position at 1680, 1670 and 1655 cm⁻¹ respectively in the free ligands, suggesting coordination through the oxygen atom of the carbonyl group^{3,4}.

νNO and δNO in free 2-picO appear at 1210 and 845 cm⁻¹ respectively. The corresponding absorptions in the spectrum of the adduct are

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PMR DATA FOR MOLECULAR ADDUCTS OF Ph_3SnNCS

Sl. No.	Adduct	M.P. °C	Analysis %				$\tau_{\text{C}_6\text{H}_5}$	τ_{OH}	τ_{CH_3}
			Sn	C	Obs (Calc)	H N			
1.	$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnNCS.TMEN}$	89	22.40 (22.70)	56.85 (57.25)	5.81 (5.91)	7.96 (8.01)	2.53 (2.02-3.05)	7.78	7.98
2.	$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnNCS.4(pn)}$	119	17.01 (16.90)	51.95 (52.84)	7.40 (7.81)	17.41 (17.89)			
3.	$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnNCS.Eu}$	102	23.90 (24.08)	53.30 (53.44)	4.30 (4.25)	8.29 (8.50)			
4.	$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnNCS.2(1-Me-2-pyr)}$	131	19.22 (19.50)	56.15 (57.42)	5.42 (5.44)	6.76 (6.98)			
5.	$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnNCS.DMF}$	109	23.12 (23.34)	54.62 (54.88)	4.06 (4.57)	5.14 (5.82)	2.52 (2.12-2.92)	—	7.26
6.	$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnNCS.2-picO}$	105	22.92 (23.01)	57.99 (58.00)	4.48 (4.25)	5.26 (5.41)			
7.	$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnNCS.HMPA}$	160	20.27 (20.19)	51.02 (51.10)	5.16 (5.62)	9.03 (9.54)	2.49 (2.08-2.90)	—	7.65 7.82
8.	$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnNCS.Bu}_2\text{SO}$	viscous	20.32 (20.87)	56.52 (56.84)	5.51 (5.78)	2.32 (2.45)			
9.	$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnNCS.DMSO}$	143	24.40 (24.45)	51.56 (51.85)	4.10 (4.32)	2.45 (2.88)	2.50 (2.08-2.92)	—	7.77
10.	$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnNCS.Atz}$	91	23.03 (23.40)	51.23 (51.96)	3.45 (3.74)	8.12 (8.26)			
11.	$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnNCS.TMTS}$	201	18.06 (18.36)	44.05 (44.44)	4.04 (4.16)	6.32 (6.50)			
12.	$\text{Ph}_3\text{SnNCS.Ph}_3\text{PS}$	131	16.54 (16.93)	62.91 (63.24)	4.14 (4.27)	1.47 (1.99)			

identified at 1195 and 830 cm^{-1} indicating oxygen atom of the ligand as the donor site.

In the spectrum of HMPA, νPO and νPN appear at 1218 and 744 cm^{-1} respectively. The negative shift of νPO (1185 cm^{-1}) and slight positive shift of νPN (748 cm^{-1}) in the spectrum of the adduct is an indication of coordination through the oxygen atom of the phosphoryl group⁵.

In the spectra of free DMSO and Bu_2SO , an absorption of strong intensity at 1045 and 947 cm^{-1} respectively has been assigned to $\text{S}=\text{O}$ stretching mode of vibrations^{4,6}. On coordination through the oxygen atom, it is shifted to lower frequency region due to a decrease in π -bonding and appears at 990 and 920 cm^{-1} in the adducts of DMSO, Bu_2SO respectively.

S-donor adducts: The appearance of νCS at 692 and 1230 cm^{-1} in free Atz and TMTS and the corresponding absorption at 680 and 1150 cm^{-1} in the spectra of their adducts is an indication of coordination through the S-atom of the 5-membered thiazole ring; and of the linear thiuramdisulphide chain respectively. Singh *et al* however, reported coordination from the nitrogen atom in the adducts of amino thiazole with Co(II) ^{7,8}.

The IR spectra of several coordination compounds of Ph_3PS with transition metals have been examined and a negative shift of νPS frequency from 637 cm^{-1} in the free ligand to about 590 cm^{-1} in the complexes has been reported. In the present investigation the corresponding absorption is identified at 610 cm^{-1} which clearly indicates the presence of the coordinated base^{9,10}.

PMR Spectra: The PMR spectra of adducts of Ph_3SnNCS with TMEN, DMF, DMSO, and HMPA show a multiplet at $\sim 2.51\tau$ (Table I) due to phenyl protons attached to the tin atom and a singlet at $\sim 7.67\tau$ due to methyl protons. The spectra and their integrations are consistent with the proposed stoichiometry of the adducts. The non-splitting of methyl protons in the case of TMEN, DMF and DMSO adducts is attributed to the free rotation about the C-N and C-S bonds, which makes the methyl groups magnetically equivalent¹¹, whereas in the case of HMPA adduct, the splitting of methylene protons (7.65, 7.82 τ) is attributed to the restricted rotation of the methyl groups.

On the basis of analytical, IR and NMR data it is suggested that molecular adducts of 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry have trigonal bipyramidal configuration containing a pentacoordinated tin atom^{12,13}. The 1 : 2 and 1 : 4 adducts of 1-Me-2-pyr and pn respectively may have a hexacoordinated tin atom with an octahedral configuration; the two additional pn molecules in $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnNCS.4pn}$ may be loosely attached through hydrogen bonding as suggested by Sakenova *et al.*¹⁴ for the adducts of SnCl_4 with ethylenediamine.

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